

Activities of Binary Molten Nitrate Mixtures

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Flory's statistical theory has been used to evaluate activity of binary molten nitrates (Li-K)NO₃ and (Li-Na)NO₃ at 573 K. Theoretical results are in fairly good agreement with experimental findings.

THE success of Flory's statistical theory¹ in predicting sound velocity and other properties of pure liquids², binary³ and ternary⁴ liquid mixtures and metallic liquids and alloys⁵ has been demonstrated during recent years. The applicability of this theory has also been extended to ionic liquids⁶⁻⁸. The present paper is concerned with the theoretical evaluation of activities of two binary molten nitrates on the basis of Flory's theory. These nitrates do not yield compounds of definite composition on solidification. For this reason, they are treated, as a first approximation, as regular solutions by Sternberg *et al.*⁹⁻¹¹. These authors determined the activities of binary molten systems. Taking clue from the successful attempts to evaluate the thermodynamic and related properties of molten systems on the basis of Flory's theory, we have made an attempt here to deduce the activities of (Li-K)NO₃ and (Li-Na)NO₃ at 573 K. The calculated values were compared with the experimental findings¹⁰.

Theoretical: The activity of binary liquid mixture can be obtained from the residual chemical potential $(\mu_1 - \mu_1^0)^{res}$. Flory theory yields the following expression for the residual chemical potential:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu_1 - \mu_1^0)^{res} = & P_1^* V_1^* \left[3\bar{T}_1 \ln \frac{(\bar{V}_1^{1/3} - 1)}{(\bar{V}_s^{1/3} - 1)} \right. \\ & \left. + \left(\frac{1}{\bar{V}_1} - \frac{1}{\bar{V}_s} \right) \right] + \left(\frac{V_1^* \cdot X_{12}}{\bar{V}_s} \right) \theta_2^s \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where subscripts 1, 2 and s refer to solvent, solute and solution respectively. $\bar{T}$ and $\bar{V}$ the reduced temperature and reduced volume are given by

$$\bar{T} = \frac{\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1}{\bar{V}^{4/3}} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\bar{V}^{1/3} = \left(\frac{\alpha T}{3\alpha T + 3} + 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

In equation (1), P^* and V^* are characteristic parameters, defined by

$$P^* = \frac{\alpha}{\beta_T} T \bar{V}^2 \quad (4)$$

and

$$V^* = V/\bar{V} \quad (5)$$

where β_T is the isothermal compressibility, α the thermal expansion coefficient and V the molar volume. The values of α , β_T and V have been taken from the different sources¹².

The interaction parameter, X_{12} , is evaluated using Berthelot's approximation,

$$X_{12} = P_1^* \left[1 - \left(\frac{V_2^*}{V_1^*} \right)^{1/6} \left(\frac{P_2^*}{P_1^*} \right)^{1/2} \right]^2 \quad (6)$$

θ_1 and θ_2 are site fractions given by,

$$\theta_2 = 1 - \theta_1 = \frac{\psi_2}{\psi_2 + \psi_1 (V_2^*/V_1^*)^{1/3}} \quad (7)$$

The activity of the component 1 in the mixture, a_1 , is given by

$$\ln a_1 = \ln(1 - \psi_2) + (1 + 1/r_0)\psi_2 + A\psi_2^2 \quad (8)$$

where ψ is the segment fraction. ψ_1 and ψ_2 are defined as

$$\psi_2 = 1 - \psi_1 = \frac{x_2}{x_2 + x_1 (V_1^*/V_2^*)} \quad (9)$$

where x_1 and x_2 represent the mole fractions of components 1 and 2, and r_0 is the segment number expressed as

$$r_0 = V_1/V_2$$

where V_1 and V_2 are the molar volumes of components 1 and 2 taken at molten salts temperature. The parameter A in equation (8) is given by,

$$A = \frac{(\mu_1 - \mu_1^0)^{res}}{RT\psi_2^2}$$

The experimental values of activity has been taken from the literature¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

From the results (Tables 1 and 2) it is evident that there is good agreement between the experimental¹⁰ and calculated values of activity. In (Li-Na)NO₃ and (Li-K)NO₃ systems the values of activity do not differ from each other, thus enforcing the fact that in uni-univalent salts the activities are

TABLE 1—ACTIVITY OF (Li-Na)NO₃ SYSTEM OF MOLTEN ELECTROLYTE AT 573 K

x_{LiNO_3}	$\bar{V}$	$a_1(\text{cal})$	$a_1(\text{expt})$	x_{NaNO_3}	$\bar{V}$	$a_1(\text{cal})$	$a_1(\text{expt})$
0.9	1.167 4	0.89	0.91	0.9	1.217 7	0.92	0.89
0.8	1.174 9	0.79	0.76	0.8	1.212 4	0.86	0.81
0.7	1.181 9	0.71	0.67	0.7	1.206 9	0.79	0.72
0.6	1.195 2	0.63	0.54	0.6	1.201 4	0.70	0.63
				0.5	1.195 2	0.67	0.52

 TABLE 2—ACTIVITY OF (Li-K)NO₃ MOLTEN SYSTEM AT 573 K

x_{LiNO_3}	$\bar{V}$	$a_1(\text{cal})$	$a_1(\text{expt})$	x_{KNO_3}	$\bar{V}$	$a_1(\text{cal})$	$a_1(\text{expt})$
0.9	1.167 4	0.89	0.91	0.9	1.217 7	0.92	0.89
0.8	1.174 9	0.79	0.76	0.8	1.212 4	0.86	0.81
0.7	1.181 9	0.71	0.67	0.7	1.206 9	0.79	0.72
0.6	1.195 2	0.63	0.54	0.6	1.201 4	0.70	0.63
				0.5	1.195 2	0.67	0.52

similar. Geometric effects also play a little role and hence size disparities⁶ should also be included in the calculations.

A minor difference between the calculated and experimental values can be explained on the basis of hole theory⁷. With the increase in the concentration of the second component the holes of the first component are gradually filled up, which bring about deviation in expansivity and compressibility and affect the calculated values.

Another reason for the deviation could be the assumption incorporated in the formulation of the interaction parameter⁷ X_{12} , the shortcoming of which have been discussed in the original publication of Flory's statistical theory¹.

On the whole, the Flory theory is applicable to molten systems and its reliability is established beyond doubt, it may therefore not be restricted to pure liquids but may also be extended to ionic systems. This feature of Flory theory again establishes the reliability of Murgulescu's^{1,8} suggestion that since ionic liquids and pure liquids have molecular parameters comparable in size the liquid state treatments which can be applied to the pure liquids are also applicable to molten systems.

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